

An improved and highly useful method for the gravimetric determination of molybdenum in molybdenum concentrates

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Abstract : The dried molybdenum concentrate is treated with hydrofluoric acid and nitric acid for its dissolution and the solution thus obtained is neutralized with ammonia and then acidified with dilute sulfuric acid. From the acidified solution molybdenum is precipitated with 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine). The precipitate is digested on a steam bath, filtered, washed with warm water and dried at 130 °C. Then it was heated in a Muffle furnace at around 600 °C, for an hour, cooled and then weighed. The product was again heated at 750 °C for about 1 h, cooled and constant weight was taken. The difference of weight (the weight of the product obtained after heating at 600 °C minus the weight of the product obtained at 750 °C) gave the actual content of molybdenum as MoO₃.

A substantial/major modification of the earlier reported 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) method for the gravimetric determination of molybdenum has been made in the proposed method.

The advantages of the proposed method over the oxine method are (i) free from most interferences, (ii) accuracy and precision of the method have been improved substantially and (iii) the results obtained from the application of the proposed method to different molybdenum concentrates are reliable.

Keywords : Molybdenum, gravimetry, 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Introduction

Determination of molybdenum is very important now-a-days due to increasing commercial and industrial application of this metal and its compound. About 86% of molybdenum produced is used in metallurgical applications such as alloys. The ability of molybdenum to withstand extreme temperatures without significantly expanding or softening makes it useful in applications that involve intense heat, including the manufacture of armor, aircraft parts, electrical contacts, industrial motors and filaments¹, most high-strength steel alloys (example 41xx steels) containing 0.25% to 8% molybdenum². More than 43,000 tonnes of molybdenum are used as an alloying agent each year in stainless steels, toolsteels, cast irons and high-temperature superalloys³. Besides these molybdenum powder is used as a fertilizer for some plants, such as cauliflower³. Elemental molybdenum is also used in NO, NO₂, NO_x analyzers in power plants for pollution controls. At 350 °C the element acts as a catalyst for NO₂/NO_x to form only NO molecules for consistent read-

ings by infrared light⁴. It has some medicinal use too. Molybdenum anodes replace tungsten in certain low voltage X-ray sources, for specialized uses such as mammography⁵ and the radioactive isotope molybdenum-99 is used to generate technetium-99, which is used for medical imaging⁶. Moreover, molybdenum is a pathfinder element for uranium Exploration⁷.

There are several methods for the determination of molybdenum by gravimetry using different reagents like *N-o*-toluoyl-*N-o*-tolylhydroxylamine⁸, pyridoin⁹, salicylhydroxamic acid¹⁰, α -benzoinoxime¹¹, lead acetate¹² and 8-hydroxyquinoline^{13,14}.

However, it has been observed that none of the methods are suitable for estimating accurately the molybdenum content of moly-concentrates. Even 8-hydroxyquinoline gravimetric method for molybdenum determination is not always yielding correct value because of presence of traces of impurities, as 8-hydroxyquinoline is known to form complexes with a host of elements, and some of these are co-precipitated along with Mo-oxinate precipi-

tate. This prompted us to re-investigate and modify suitably the well known oxine method for the determination of Mo in molybdenum-concentrates by heating the Mo-oxinate complex at around 600 °C. Oxine is oxidized to CO₂ and NO_x and Mo gets converted into MoO₃ which can be weighed and molybdenum can be estimated. However, this oxide is usually not free from impurities because of the reasons cited above. The actual content of molybdenum is accurately found out by heating the impure oxide above 750 °C whereby, Mo gets completely evaporated and lost, leaving the impurities as residue. The difference in weight of the oxides at these two temperatures i.e. 600 °C and 750 °C gives us the accurate content of molybdenum in the sample.

The present paper encompasses the studies on the precipitation of molybdenum with oxine, and its purification by subliming Mo at higher temperature.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A digital quantitative weighing balance (Sartorius make). A Muffle furnace and silica crucibles.

Reagents :

All the reagents used were of AR grade unless otherwise specified.

Oxine solution (3%) in dilute acetic acid :

Dissolved 3 g oxine in 8.5 ml warm glacial acetic acid, pouring into 80 ml water and diluted to 100 ml.

H₂SO₄ acid, 1 mol L⁻¹.

Ammonium acetate, 2 mol L⁻¹ for pH adjustment.

Procedure :

Dissolution of molybdenum-concentrates :

A 1.0 g of dried molybdenum-concentrate was weighed accurately into a teflon beaker and treated with 10 ml of hydrofluoric acid and 5 ml of nitric acid on a hot plate. After evaporation the sample was again treated with another 10 ml portion of hydrofluoric acid to completely remove silica, and then excess fluoride was removed by treating with 5 ml nitric acid. Finally the clear solution was made upto 100 ml in a calibrated volumetric flask.

Precipitation of molybdenum with 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) :

A 20 ml of the solution was taken into a 250 ml bea-

ker. Then the solution was neutralized with ammonia using methyl red as indicator, then acidified with 2 to 3 drops of 1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ acid, then 5 ml of 2 mol L⁻¹ ammonium acetate was added to obtain desired pH (3–6). The solution was diluted to ~100 ml, and it was heated till boiling. After that molybdenum was precipitated with the addition of 3% oxine solution in dilute acetic acid until the supernatant liquid became yellow. Then the solution was boiled gently and stirred for three minutes. The solution was filtered through a filtering crucible, and washed with hot water until free from reagent, then it was dried.

Conversion of Mo-oxine precipitate into MoO₃ :

After drying the precipitate on filter paper it was taken in a previously weighed silica crucible and heated at 100 °C. Constant weight of the crucible was taken and then it was heated at around 600 °C for 1 h, and then constant weight of the crucible was taken after cooling. Thereafter, the residue was heated at 750 °C for 1 h, cooled and weighed to a constant weight. The difference between the two weights (after heating at 600 °C and 750 °C) gave the amount of molybdenum lost during heating.

Results and discussion

8-Hydroxyquinoline (oxine) is known to form complexes with a host of elements such as Al, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mo, V, Ni, Co etc. at different pH conditions¹⁵, some are soluble and few are insoluble. The insoluble complexes of these elements have been made use of in the gravimetric determination of the respective elements, although the precipitation of these compounds are more or less pH dependent. However, inter elemental interferences are always there, thereby rendering the gravimetric methods for determinations of these elements not quite selective. However, the precipitation of Mo-oxine complex which is formed in the pH range, 3.3 to 7.6 seems to be quite selective and elements like Fe, Al, Cu, Ni etc. are not supposed to form oxine precipitate over this pH range. Based upon this strategy a well known gravimetric method for Mo determination is in vogue¹⁶. By adopting this method we tried to estimate Mo in a number of molybdenum concentrates received from UCIL, Jaduguda Milling and Mining sites. As per our observations, even after scrupulously following the method given in literature¹⁶ the results obtained were found not very satisfac-

tory. This might be because of co-precipitation of other elements along with Mo. As per the procedure, the Mo-oxine precipitate is dried at 130 °C and the dried complex is weighed as such, and from the established stoichiometry of the complex (i.e. $\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2$), Mo content was calculated/found out. However, owing to co-precipitation of certain elements, the results obtained for Mo determination was found to be invariably inaccurate i.e. always higher values were obtained vis-a-vis those obtained by other standard methods. In order to verify this aspect, a set of three different synthetic mixtures of different compositions were prepared (as shown in the Table 1) and this gravimetric method was applied to these synthetic mixtures for gravimetric determination of molybdenum. It is very clear from the data shown in the table that the elements which are supposed to be present along with molybdenum in concentrates, interfere in its determination by oxine method, and always higher values of Mo than those actually present were obtained because other elements also co-precipitate along with Mo. More the contents of these elements more is the % error. This is clearly observable from the results tabulated in Table 1. This fact was further attested when the oxine method was applied to two different Mo-concentrates (E-6 and E-29) received from milling and mining sites of UCIL, Jaduguda. Here, too, similar results i.e. higher values of Mo than those reported by standard methods were found giving rise to an error of the order of 11–12%.

This short of discrepancies are amply shown in an International Standard ISO paper 4173–80¹⁴ for gravimetric determination of Mo content in ferromolybdenum where iron has been cited as the most interfering element, and in order to accurately determine Mo in such samples prior removal of iron was recommended.

In order to avoid the interferences of most concomitant elements in the oxine method, a highly useful modification has been brought about in the proposed system. Here the Mo-oxine complex infested with impurities of other concomitant elements which also form oxine complexes was heated at ~600 °C whereby oxine got burnt away with the evolution of CO_2 and NO_x leaving Mo as MoO_3 along with metal oxides of other impurities. The constant weight of this residue was taken and the same (residue) was further heated at 750 °C whereby Mo was completely eliminated as volatile MoO_3 . However, the

impurities left in the crucible was weighed. The difference of the two weights gives the actual content of Mo in the sample.

Molybdenum gets completely evaporated at a temperature 700 °C and above but no other elements have got this property. This unique property of Mo has been exploited to our advantage in order to accurately determine Mo in molybdenum containing substrates like molybdenum-concentrates. By making use of this system all the interfering elements encountered in the gravimetric determination of molybdenum have been completely eliminated thereby making the proposed method highly selective.

The present modified system has been applied to the determination of Mo in two different molybdenum-concentrates (E-6 and E-29) and results obtained as shown in Table 4 have been found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by other standard methods.

The data shown in Table 3 are obtained when the proposed method was applied to the very synthetic mixtures wherein the oxine method was applied. Comparing the result of Table 1 with Table 3, it clearly shows that the proposed method is free from interference (error ranged from 0.65 to 1.3%) when applied to synthetic mixtures unlike the result obtained by the oxine method, where error of determination was in the range of 7–63%. It shows that how effective the present method is.

Effect of other elements in the determination of molybdenum :

As against the claim that the oxine method is very selective for molybdenum determination, it has been found by us (Table 1) that elements like Fe, Cu, Ni, Zn, Al, Ca, Mg, Mn etc. interfere seriously by the oxine method. With the increase in concentration of these elements, degree of interference also increases. Depending on the concentration of these elements as present in three different synthetic mixtures, the degree of error in the determination of molybdenum by oxine method is increased by 7.23, 38.03 and 63.44% respectively. However, interestingly, when the proposed method was applied to these synthetic mixtures, the recovery of molybdenum were, 99.06, 98.66 and 99.35% respectively (Table 3) demonstrating that the proposed method is much more superior to oxine method, in terms of accuracy of the results obtained.

Table 1. Determinations of Mo in synthetic mixtures by oxinate method

Solution	Mo added	Metal ions	Composition	Wt at 130 °C as oxinate	Theoretically expected value of Mo for 100% recovery	Positive error (%)
Solution A	50 mg	Fe	5 mg	232.6 mg	216.9 mg	7.23
		Zn	1 mg			
		Ca	1 mg			
		V	0.5 mg			
		Cu	1 mg			
		Ni	1 mg			
		Mn	1 mg			
		Al	1 mg			
		Li	0.5 mg			
		Co	1 mg			
		U	1 µg			
		La	0.5 mg			
		Solution B	50 mg			
Zn	5 mg					
Ca	5 mg					
V	1 mg					
Cu	2 mg					
Ni	2 mg					
Mn	5 mg					
Al	5 mg					
Li	1 mg					
Co	2 mg					
U	5 µg					
La	1 mg					
Solution C	50 mg			Fe	20 mg	354.5 mg
		Zn	10 mg			
		Ca	10 mg			
		V	2 mg			
		Cu	5 mg			
		Ni	5 mg			
		Mn	10 mg			
		Al	10 mg			
		Li	2 mg			
		Co	5 mg			
		U	10 µg			
		La	2 mg			

Table 2. Determination of molybdenum in moly-concentrates by oxinate method

Sample no.	Wt. of oxinate at 130 °C (g)	% of Mo	Reported value (thiocyanate spectrophotometry)	% Error
E-6	1.9906	46.8	41.8	11.96
E-29	2.0534	47.4	42	12.86

Table 3. Determination of molybdenum in synthetic mixtures by proposed method

Solutions	Wt. in mg at 600 °C (W ₁)	Wt. in mg at 750 °C (W ₂)	W ₁ -W ₂	% Recovery
Solution A	85.6	11.3	74.3	99.06
Solution B	151.6	77.6	74.0	98.66
Solution C	232.6	158.1	74.5	99.35

Table 4. Determination of molybdenum in moly-concentrates by proposed method

Sample no.	% of Mo	% RSD	Reported value (thiocyanate spectrophotometry)
E-6	40.6	0.34	41.8
E-29	41.9	1.3	42

As molybdenum is usually associated with tungsten and uranium, particularly in sulfide minerals, it was incumbent on us to see the effect of these two elements in the determination of molybdenum in molybdenum-concentrates, the results of the studies as shown in Tables 5 and 6, respectively clearly show that there is no interference of these two elements in the determination of molybdenum. In other words, it can be said that at the temperature of molybdenum oxide volatilisation i.e. in the temperature range 600–720 °C tungsten as well as

Table 5. Effect of tungsten on determination of molybdenum

Solution	Composition (mg)		Weight loss (g)	Percentage recovery (%)
	Mo	W	$\Delta W = W_{720^{\circ}\text{C}} - W_{600^{\circ}\text{C}}$	
Solution D	50	5	0.741	98.80
Solution E	50	2	0.742	98.93
Solution F	0	20	0.001	-

Table 6. Effect of uranium on determination of molybdenum

Solution	Composition (mg)		Weight loss (g)	Percentage recovery (%)
	Mo	U	$\Delta W = W_{720^{\circ}\text{C}} - W_{600^{\circ}\text{C}}$	
Solution G	50	5	0.741	98.80

uranium is not volatile. Tables 5 and 6 show that recovery of molybdenum are about 98 to 99%, Fig. 1 also attests to the above fact.

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on the volatilisation of molybdenum and tungsten.

Fig. 2. Profile of weight loss of moly-oxine complex with the rise in temperature.

Effect of the temperature in the volatilisation of molybdenum :

When moly-oxine and entrapped oxine complexes of interfering elements are heated at 600 °C, oxine gets oxidized to CO₂ and NO_x and molybdenum and the interfering metals gets converted to respective oxides. When the temperature is raised to 750 °C and above MoO₃ gets evaporated leaving the impurities of other metal oxides. Raising of temperature above 750 °C does not bring about any change in the result and at a temperature lower than 600 °C Mo is not volatile. Therefore, temperature plays a very crucial role in the determination of molybdenum by this technique. The profile of the loss of the moly-oxine complex with the rise in temperature was also studied. Fig. 2 shows the profile. It clearly shows at temperature of 100–130 °C moisture/entrapped water is lost. At about 200–300 °C the loss shown is due to ashing of filter paper. However, when the temperature is raised to

450–570 °C oxine is oxidized and lost. On further raising the temperature, molybdenum as MoO₃ is lost in the temperature range of 600–750 °C.

Precision of the method :

The method being reported here is highly precise as evidenced by an RSD of 0.3 to 1.3% for a sample containing molybdenum in the range 35 to 45%.

Conclusions

A substantial improvement has been made over the oxine-gravimetric determination of Mo. The method is highly reproducible (precision is excellent) and free from most interferences encountered in the oxine gravimetric method for Mo determination. It is even better than the International Standard ISO method for molybdenum estimation for ferromolybdenum because, this, too is prone to serious interference of iron. The present method is so robust that it can be applied to any kind of samples and

the results obtained for Mo determinations in all the samples are highly accurate.

Recommendations :

Based upon the findings, the authors recommend this method for routine analysis of Mo over a wide range in almost all the samples containing Mo.

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